

Digital Repositories

You found a test! You better not disappoint Prof. Hutseephluts and answer all the questions correctly or you may never see daylight again!

*Vereist

What are reasons to archive your research data?

1. Multiple answers possible. *

Vink alle toepasselijke opties aan.

- Long-term preservation
- Replication/reproducibility
- Longitudinal research
- The data are unique or new data collection is expensive
- Re-usability by your future-self or other researchers
- Acceleration of research inside or outside your own discipline
- Funders ask you to
- To protect it from zombies

Which of the following should data repositories minimally provide?

2. Multiple answers possible. *

Vink alle toepasselijke opties aan.

- A persistent identifier (e.g. DOI, Handle), which provides a permanent link to the data, making your data findable and citable.
- A licence, providing clarity for the potential user of your data whether and how re-use of your data is permitted.
- A (basic) preservation and data availability statement.
- The requirement to add appropriate metadata to the data.

True or False? The website Re3data (re3data.org) can be used to find a suitable data repository for your discipline.

3. Write your answer as True or False. *

True or False? GitHub (github.com) can be used as a publicly accessible platform with version control for research software/code.

4. Write your answer as True or False. *

You want to make your data publicly available. What are FAIR ways to do this? Multiple answers possible.

A) Have a pack of werewolves spread your data across the country.

B) Share a dropbox link to the data with anyone that requests access.

C) Upload the data to a repository like DANS-EASY, DataVerseNL, or 4TU.ResearchData.

D) Email the data to your colleagues and peers.

E) Upload the data to the Open Science Framework (OSF).

5. Write your answer as ABC... *

A)
4TU.ResearchData

You are looking for a repository that stores data in the Netherlands. What are good options? Multiple answers possible.

B) DANS EASY

C) Zenodo

D) Dryad

E) DataverseNL

F) The Addams Family Mansion

6. Write your answer as ABC... *

True or False? If there is no licence, this means that anyone can do anything with the data.

7. Write your answer as True or False. *

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